

Theoretical Insights into the Spectroscopic Properties and Prospects for the Direct Laser Cooling of the Radium Monohalides

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Alkaline earth metal monohalides are currently considered the most promising candidates for direct laser cooling due to the unique electronic structure of their lower states. Among the alkaline earth monohalides family, the radium compounds are of the highest interest because of the largest mass of the radium atom compared to other alkaline earth metals, which provides some advantages for applications of ultracold matter. In addition, the radium monohalides are still the least studied both theoretically and experimentally. Here the state-of-the-art *ab initio* studies of the lower states of radium monochloride RaCl and radium monoastatide RaAt diatomic radicals are presented for the first time. The potential energy curves of the ground and five low-lying excited states are calculated using the Fock-space relativistic coupled cluster method. Electronic term energies, equilibrium internuclear distances, transition and permanent dipole moments, sequences of vibrational energies, harmonic vibrational frequencies, Franck-Condon factors, and radiative lifetimes are predicted. Based on these results, we calculated cooling parameters for all radium monohalides and concluded that all of them, including the RaAt molecule, can be used for direct laser cooling. The probable vibrational laser cooling schemes were also proposed. This work continues the series of research of radium monohalides and includes the comparison of results with previously studied RaF, RaBr, and RaI molecules. It can provide an understanding of trends in spectroscopic and radiative properties of this alkaline earth metal monohalides series.

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1. Introduction

During the last decades, the unique properties of ultracold diatomic molecules are considered to be used for manifold potential applications including controlling dipole-dipole interactions between two or more molecules, quantum information processing, control of collisions and chemical reactions, and some

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other (for details see the recent review [1]). New promising applications of ultracold molecules (both di- and polyatomic) also include the research on parity violation effects, namely, the possibility of observation of an electron's electric dipole moment (eEDM) [1, 2]. In the latter case measured parameters critically depend on the atomic mass, and thus, for these goals it is preferable to use heavy atoms, which often do not have stable isotopes. The mentioned applications require ultralow temperatures of molecular gasses, which can be reached using laser cooling methods, including direct laser cooling [1].

The principles of direct laser cooling of molecules are similar to the ideas for laser slowing and trapping of atoms and are based on scattering (absorption and re-emission) of a large number of photons by a molecule. Successful realization of a closed (or quasi-closed) cooling optical scheme requires the fulfillment of Di Rosa's criteria [3] for a for a potential molecule, including the following conditions:

1. Strong transition dipole moment (TDM) between the states involved in the cooling scheme;
2. Close coincidence of the equilibrium internuclear distances of corresponding potential energy curves (PECs), that leads to highly diagonal overlapping matrices between vibrational eigenfunctions of the ground and some excited electronic states (or, in other words, large values of the diagonal Franck-Condon factors, FCFs);
3. Absence of intervening electronic states between the low-lying terms to avoid leaks in the cooling cycle.

For the practical realization of the cooling scheme the availability of a continuous tunable laser source in an appropriate spectral region is also essential.

Among numerous promising candidates for the successful realization of the cooling scheme, the alkaline earth monohalides look the most attractive for their unique electronic structure of the ground and low-lying excited states. It is determined by excitation of the valence ns

electron of the metal atom to the np or $(n-1)d$ state in the ionic M^+X^- structure (where $M = \text{Be, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, or Ra}$; $X = \text{F, Cl, Br, I, or At}$) [4, 5]. As a result, excitation of the valence electrons almost does not influence the form of the low-lying PECs. They are symmetrical and close to parallel in the region of minima and have a pronounced ionic character.

Recently, based on the unique spectroscopic properties of the monohalides of alkaline earth metals, strontium monofluoride SrF [6–8] and calcium monofluoride CaF [9–13] radicals were successfully cooled and caught into a magneto-optical trap.

Due to the largest mass of the radium atom compared to other alkaline earth metal atoms, the radium compounds are of the highest interest among the alkaline earth monohalides family in terms of the possible determination of eEDM. The first ionization energy of the radium atom is one of the smallest in the series of alkaline earth metals [14] that causes the ultimate similarity of the lowest excited molecular terms with the PEC of the ground state. However, due to the high degree of radioactivity of radium and the absence of its stable isotopes, the radium monohalides are the least experimentally studied. Until the early 2020s, there was only one experimental spectroscopic study of the molecular radium monohalide, namely, its monochloride RaCl [15].

A recent breakthrough experiment with RaF [16, 17] made it possible to determine the spectroscopic molecular parameters of the ground and lower excited ionic states of this molecule with high accuracy for the first time. Therefore, it is possible to use these data to verify and refine theoretical results both for this molecule and its analogues.

Along with experimental achievement, several theoretical studies were dedicated to investigating the parameters of parity violation effects [2, 18–21], hyperfine structure [18, 19, 22], and value of permanent dipole moment (PDM) [2, 19, 23] of the radium monofluoride ground state. Some molecular spectroscopic parameters of the ground $X^2\Sigma^+$ and low-lying excited

terms of the RaF molecule were calculated by Borschevsky *et al.* [24], Kudashov *et al.* [25], Vasiliu *et al.* [26], Sunaga *et al.* [2], Isaev *et al.* [27], Isaev and Berger [28], Skripnikov [29], and Zaitsevskii *et al.* [30]. For the ground state of the RaCl molecule the heat of formation was experimentally obtained by obtained by Lawson [31] and Ponomarev *et al.* [32], and some molecular spectroscopic parameters were calculated by Vasiliu *et al.* [26] and Sunaga *et al.* [2].

Recently, Isaev *et al.* [33] have calculated the main spectroscopic parameters of the ground $X^2\Sigma^+$ and low-lying ionic excited term of the RaCl molecule, as well as the parameters of its parity violation effects. To the best of our knowledge, up to 2020s the only one theoretical research on the radium monobromide RaBr, radium monoiodide RaI, and radium monoastatide RaAt molecules was dedicated to investigating the parameters of P - and T , P -odd terms, the value of PDM, rotational constant, and the ground state equilibrium internuclear distance [2] and no experimental data is available for the lowest electronic states of these molecules.

Lately, we carried out the state-of-the-art MRPT (Multi-Reference Perturbation Theory) calculations at the non-relativistic CASSCF/XMCQDPT2 (Complete Active Space Self-Consistent Field / Extended Multi-Configuration Quasi-Degenerate 2nd Order Perturbation Theory) [34] level of theory for the RaCl [35] molecule. The mentioned approach, supplemented by consideration of spin-orbit coupling (SOC) as a perturbation at the last step of calculations, provides sufficient accuracy for the compounds containing atoms from the middle of the Periodic Table (see, e.g. [36, 37]). Generally, heavier atoms require a relativistic treatment, including both scalar and vector relativistic effects from the outset. These goals can be achieved using *ab initio* FS-RCC (Fock-space relativistic coupled cluster) [38] method.

Regarding the CASSCF/XMCQDPT2 + SOC results for the RaCl molecule [34], the

PECs of the ground and eight low-lying excited ionic and covalent terms were calculated. The electronic term energies, equilibrium internuclear distances, dissociation energies, transition dipole moments, sequences of vibrational energies, harmonic vibrational frequencies, FCFs, and radiative lifetimes were predicted. It was also shown that at the large internuclear distances the ionic terms are strongly perturbed by the non-bonded covalent ones. For the most part, the characteristics of the PECs in the region of minima do not contradict Lagerqvist's experimental data [15] and later calculations at the FC-RCC level of theory [33].

Recently, we also used the FC-RCC level of theory to obtain spectroscopic properties of the ground and five low-lying excited states of the RaF [39], RaBr [40], and RaI [41] radicals as well as transport properties of two-component dilute gas media of radium and halogen atoms [42]. Our calculations for the RaF molecule [39] demonstrate an excellent agreement with the experimental data [16, 17] and their reassignment [30]. The deviations of the predicted $A^2\Pi_{1/2}$, $B^2\Delta_{3/2}$, $A^2\Pi_{3/2}$, and $C^2\Sigma^+$ terms energy from the experimental ones are -25 , -149 , -42 , and -27 cm^{-1} for the cc-pCVTZ basis set and $+10$, -170 , -23 , and -7 cm^{-1} for the cc-pwCVTZ basis set.

Based on these results we predicted laser cooling parameters and proposed a scheme for direct laser cooling involving the ground $X^2\Sigma^+$ and first excited $A^2\Pi_{1/2}$ states not only for the RaF radical but also for the RaBr and RaI ones, and considered the main trends for the radium monohalides in relation to the prospects of their direct laser cooling. The radium monochloride falls out from trends since our previous calculations on RaCl [35] were carried out at a different level of theory and calculations by Isaev *et al.* [33] were carried out using other families of effective core potentials (ECPs) and basis sets. There are no cooling parameters for radium monoastatide at all.

To fill in these blanks here we use the FC-RCCSD level of theory to calculate PECs,

TDMs, and other spectroscopic and radiative characteristics of the RaCl and RaAt radicals, as well as clarify the advantages of the various radium monohalides compounds from the point of view of their effective direct laser cooling. Our previous results on RaF [39], RaBr [40], and RaI [41] molecules are also supplemented and partially corrected.

2. Computational details

Ab initio relativistic calculations were performed using FS-RCCSD (Fock-space relativistic coupled cluster singles and doubles) [38] method for the ground and excited states. Nowadays, the FS-RCC approach is one of the most successful tools for predicting the electronic structure and properties of molecular compounds containing heavy atoms. It provides the most accurate data on PECs and other characteristics of excited states of small molecular systems.

Within the FS-RCC approach, an effective Hamiltonian is defined in a model space, which is constructed from Slaters determinants. A reference zero-order wave function (or vacuum state) is a closed-shell determinant, and the operator of the excitation is defined relative to the vacuum state and divided into parts according to the number of valence holes and valence electrons.

In case of an alkaline earth monohalide MX molecule, the vacuum state is the closed-shell positively charged ion MX^+ (or 0 holes and 0 electrons over vacuum). Thus, the first step of calculations for an alkaline earth monohalide molecule in the FS-RCC approach is a solution of the coupled cluster equations for a closed-shell reference ion (or (0,0) Fock sector). The final step is adding an electron and solving the coupled cluster equations for an open-shell neutral MX molecule (or (0,1) Fock sector).

Calculations were started by generating pseudospinors at the HF-SCF level of theory for the closed-shell ground state of RaCl^+ and RaAt^+ ions. Then the FS-RCCSD calculations in the (0,1) Fock sector (0 holes, 1 electron, or 1 particle

over vacuum) were performed for the RaCl^+ and RaAt^+ ions for six low-lying states.

The Stuttgart ECPDS78MDFSO fully relativistic large effective core potentials (ECP) [43] and ECPDS60MDFSO fully relativistic small ECP [44] were used for the radium and astatine atoms, respectively. The ECPs [43, 44] replace 78 and 60 chemically inactive core electrons for the radium and astatine atoms with empirical pseudo-potentials. They also include the spin-orbit parameters and take into account the Breit interaction in the computational scheme.

The Gaussian all-electron cc-pCVTZ [7s6p4d2f] [45] basis set and cc-pwCVTZ-PP [7s6p5d3f] [46] and cc-pwCVTZ-PP [7s6p5d3f1g] [47] basis sets were used for the chlorine atom and the remaining radium and astatine electrons, respectively. All 10 remaining electrons of the radium atom, as well as all 17 electrons of the chlorine atom and all remaining 25 electrons of the astatine atom were included in correlation calculations. The active space in FS-RCCSD calculations was limited to energy up to $1000 E_h$.

For the RaCl radical the calculations were performed pointwise for the 2.200–5.000 Å internuclear distances by step of 0.025 Å in the minima region (2.200–4.000 Å) and by step of 0.100 Å outside of the mentioned region. For the RaAt radical the calculations were performed pointwise for the 2.500–5.000 Å internuclear distances by step of 0.025 Å in the minima region (2.900–3.700 Å) and by step of 0.100 Å outside of the mentioned region.

The direct evaluation of PDMs and TDMs is not implemented in the FS-RCC method. Therefore, the calculations of the TDMs and PDMs were performed at the MRCI/cc-pCVTZ or MRCI/cc-pwCVTZ level of theory. The MRCI method provides sufficient accuracy for the prediction of radiative properties for the PECs, which are far from avoided crossing points [48].

All calculations of PECs, PDMs, and TDMs were performed using the DIRAC19 quantum chemical package [49]. The electronic energy terms T_e and the equilibrium internuclear distances R_e were obtained using the second-

degree polynomial approximation of the *ab initio* PECs near their minima. The calculations of the vibrational state energies and the Franck–Condon factors were performed using the LEVEL program package [50].

The errors for calculated values have all been rounded to their typical experimental precision, which are indicated in parentheses after the corresponding values: T_e , ΔE_{SOC} (1 cm^{-1}); R_e ($1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ \AA}$); PDM (1×10^{-2} Debye); ω_e ($1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$); $\omega_e \chi_e$ ($1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^{-1}$); B_e ($1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$); $f_{v'v''}$, $b_{v'v''}$ (1×10^{-6}); A_0 ($1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ s}^{-1}$); τ_0 ($1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ ns}$); v_r ($1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm/s}$); v_{room} , v_{3K} (1 m/s); N_{room} , N_{3K} , N_{ph} (1); T_D^{min} (1 \mu K); T_r (1 nK); T_D , T_D^{opt} ($1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mK}$);

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electronic and vibrational states

The calculated lowest PECs for all radium monohalides are shown in Fig. 1, their parameters are collected and compared with experimental and previous theoretical studies in Table 1. Systems of the lowest ionic terms of the radicals under consideration are similar in the minima region. Their behavior at the largest internuclear distances depends on the higher lying covalent states [34] and is not considered here.

The equilibrium internuclear distances in the series of $\text{RaF} \rightarrow \text{RaCl} \rightarrow \text{RaBr} \rightarrow \text{RaI} \rightarrow \text{RaAt}$ monotonously increase:

- 2.269-2.287 \AA for RaF [39];
- 2.813-2.828 \AA for RaCl;
- 2.986-3.001 \AA for RaBr [40];
- 3.214-3.230 \AA for RaI [41];
- 3.307-3.325 \AA for RaAt.

The energies of all excited terms monotonously decrease. The sequence of the lowest PECs is the same ($X^2\Sigma^+$, $A^2\Pi_{1/2}$, $B^2\Delta_{3/2}$, $B^2\Delta_{5/2}$, $A^2\Pi_{3/2}$, and $C^2\Sigma^+$) for all radium monohalides, excluding the RaF radical, for which according to our calculations [39] the $A^2\Pi_{3/2}$ term ($15\,332 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) lies lower than the $B^2\Delta_{5/2}$ one ($15\,740 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Our predicted energy of the $B^2\Delta_{3/2}$ term ($14\,978 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is slightly underestimated relative to the experimental value ($15\,148 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) [16], while Zaitsevskii *et al.* [30] energy ($14\,352 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is underestimated more significantly. Hence, the $B^2\Delta_{5/2}$ term should be located over the $A^2\Pi_{3/2}$ term, with the predicted position ($15\,332 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [39], $15\,348 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [30]) that agrees with the experimental energy ($15\,355 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [16]).

According to Zaitsevskii *et al.* [30] calculations, the RaF PECs demonstrate the same order of terms as the other radium monohalides, and the $A^2\Pi_{3/2}$ term ($15\,348 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) lies higher than the $B^2\Delta_{5/2}$ one ($15\,151 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Note, that the $B^2\Delta_{5/2}$ term is the only one for which the energy has not been determined experimentally.

The position of this term can be evaluated using the SOC splitting between components of the $B^2\Delta_{3/2,5/2}$ term.

Based on our calculations this value is 762 cm^{-1} [39] and it agrees with Zaitsevskii *et al.* [30] one (799 cm^{-1}) and with SOC splitting values for other radium monohalides (see below).

The splitting between components of $A^2\Pi_{1/2,3/2}$ and $B^2\Delta_{3/2,5/2}$ terms due to the spin-orbit coupling is shown in Fig. 2.

The SOC splitting of the $A^2\Pi$ term $\Delta E_{SOC}(A^2\Pi) = E(A^2\Pi_{3/2}) - E(A^2\Pi_{1/2})$ near minima positions of the PECs is of the same order for all radium monohalides:

- 2068/2050 cm^{-1} for RaF (exp.[16]/theor.[39]);
- 2094 cm^{-1} for RaCl;
- 2124 cm^{-1} for RaBr [40];
- 2120 cm^{-1} for RaI [41];
- 2154 cm^{-1} for RaAt.

The SOC splitting of the $B^2\Delta$ term $\Delta E_{SOC}(B^2\Delta) = E(B^2\Delta_{5/2}) - E(B^2\Delta_{3/2})$ near minima positions of the PECs is equal to:

- 762 cm^{-1} for RaF [39];
- 897 cm^{-1} for RaCl;
- 932 cm^{-1} for RaBr [40];
- 959 cm^{-1} for RaI [41];
- 918 cm^{-1} for RaAt.

Calculated PDMs as the functions of

FIG. 1. (Color online) The dependencies of calculated potential energies upon internuclear distances for the low-lying states of the RaF [39] (a), RaCl (b), RaBr [40] (c), RaI [41] (d), and RaAt (e) molecules.

internuclear distances are shown in Fig. 3. Their values for equilibrium internuclear distances are listed in Table 1.

For the ground state all of them are underestimated relative to Sunaga *et al.* [2] data, which is explained by the difference in the approximations used.

Radium has no stable isotopes, the longest-lived isotope of radium is ^{226}Ra with a half-life of about 1600 years. Fluorine has only one stable isotope, namely ^{19}F . Chlorine has two stable isotopes (^{35}Cl and ^{37}Cl) with abundances of 76 % and 24 %, respectively. Bromine also has two stable isotopes (^{79}Br and ^{81}Br) with abundances of 51 % and 49 %, respectively. Iodine is a monoisotopic element. It has only one ^{127}I

stable isotope. Astatine has no stable isotopes; the longest-lived isotope of astatine is ^{210}At with a half-life of about 8 hours.

We calculated the vibrational energies for the $^{226}\text{Ra}^{35}\text{Cl}$, $^{226}\text{Ra}^{37}\text{Cl}$, and $^{226}\text{Ra}^{210}\text{At}$ radicals for six low-lying PECs and then obtained the harmonic vibrational frequencies ω_e and other molecular spectroscopic parameters for these electronic states. Main molecular spectroscopic parameters of the $^{226}\text{Ra}^{35}\text{Cl}$ and $^{226}\text{Ra}^{210}\text{At}$ as well as calculated earlier for the $^{226}\text{Ra}^{19}\text{F}$ [39], $^{226}\text{Ra}^{79}\text{Br}$ [40], and $^{226}\text{Ra}^{127}\text{I}$ [41] molecules are collected in Table 2.

Fig. 4 shows vibrational energies E_v for the low-lying states of the $^{226}\text{Ra}^{19}\text{F}$, $^{226}\text{Ra}^{35}\text{Cl}$, $^{226}\text{Ra}^{79}\text{Br}$, $^{226}\text{Ra}^{127}\text{I}$, and $^{226}\text{Ra}^{210}\text{At}$ molecules.

Table 1: Parameters of the potential energy curves and permanent dipole moments of the lowest states of the radium monohalides molecules.

State	RaF			RaCl			RaBr			RaI			RaAt		
	T_e , cm $^{-1}$	R_e , Å	PDM, D	T_e , cm $^{-1}$	R_e , Å	PDM, D	T_e , cm $^{-1}$	R_e , Å	PDM, D	T_e , cm $^{-1}$	R_e , Å	PDM, D	T_e , cm $^{-1}$	R_e , Å	PDM, D
$X^2\Sigma^+$	0			0			0			0			0		
		2.272 ^{a)}	4.070 ⁱ⁾		2.817 ^{l)}	5.200 ^{o)}		2.987 ^{p)}	5.840 ^{q)}		3.224 ^{r)}	6.060 ^{s)}		3.325 ^{l)}	5.980 ^{o)}
		2.243 ^{b)}	4.500 ^{h)}		2.792 ^{g)}	6.100 ^{h)}		2.970 ^{h)}	6.300 ^{h)}		3.230 ^{h)}	6.900 ^{h)}		3.330 ^{h)}	6.700 ^{h)}
		2.255 ^{c)}	3.800 ^{j)}		2.820 ^{h)}	7.620 ^{m)}									
		2.243 ^{d)}	3.620 ^{k)}		2.776 ^{m)}										
$A^2\Pi_{1/2}$		2.238 ^{f)}			2.789 ⁿ⁾										
	13 298 ^{a)}	2.300 ^{h)}													
	<u>13 288</u> ^{t)}	2.273 ^{a)}			2.813 ^{l)}	4.460 ^{o)}		2.986 ^{p)}	4.830 ^{q)}		3.214 ^{r)}	4.860 ^{s)}		3.307 ^{l)}	4.760 ^{o)}
	14 012 ^{b)}	2.243 ^{b)}	4.000 ⁱ⁾		2.802 ^{m)}	7.250 ^{m)}									
	14 000 ^{d)}	2.243 ^{d)}			2.792 ⁿ⁾										
$B^2\Delta_{3/2}$	13 300 ^{e)}	2.269 ^{e)}													
	13 303 ^{v)}	2.248 ^{v)}													
	14 978 ^{a)}	2.285 ^{a)}			2.828 ^{l)}	9.360 ^{o)}		3.001 ^{p)}	10.02 ^{q)}		3.230 ^{r)}	10.23 ^{s)}		3.322 ^{l)}	10.04 ^{o)}
	<u>15 148</u> ^{t)}	2.248 ^{d)}	7.970 ⁱ⁾		2.803 ^{m)}	8.730 ^{m)}									
	16 400 ^{d)}	2.264 ^{e)}			2.800 ⁿ⁾										
$B^2\Delta_{5/2}$	15 400 ^{e)}	2.258 ^{v)}													
	14 352 ^{v)}														
	15 740 ^{a)}	2.280 ^{a)}			2.821 ^{l)}	9.360 ^{o)}		2.993 ^{p)}	10.02 ^{q)}		3.221 ^{r)}	10.25 ^{s)}		3.313 ^{l)}	10.07 ^{o)}
	17 100 ^{d)}	2.259 ^{d)}	7.970 ⁱ⁾		2.767 ^{m)}	8.73 ^{m)}									
	15 800 ^{e)}	2.275 ^{e)}			2.794 ⁿ⁾										
$A^2\Pi_{3/2}$	15 151 ^{v)}	2.253 ^{v)}													
	15 332 ^{a)}	2.269 ^{a)}			2.813 ^{l)}	4.480 ^{o)}		2.987 ^{p)}	4.830 ^{q)}		3.218 ^{r)}	4.810 ^{s)}		3.311 ^{l)}	4.490 ^{o)}
	<u>15 355</u> ^{t)}	2.248 ^{d)}	4.040 ⁱ⁾		2.818 ^{m)}	7.250 ^{m)}									
	16 000 ^{d)}	2.280 ^{e)}			2.793 ⁿ⁾										
	15 000 ^{e)}	2.243 ^{v)}													
$C^2\Sigma^+$	15 348 ^{v)}														
	16 614 ^{a)}	2.287 ^{a)}			2.822 ^{l)}	0.750 ^{o)}		2.991 ^{p)}	0.195 ^{q)}		3.215 ^{r)}	0.060 ^{s)}		3.307 ^{l)}	0.340 ^{o)}
	<u>16 621</u> ^{t)}	2.254 ^{d)}	1.180 ⁱ⁾		2.809 ^{m)}	5.150 ^{m)}									
	18 100 ^{d)}	2.285 ^{e)}			2.800 ⁿ⁾										
	16 700 ^{e)}	2.263 ^{v)}													
16 644 ^{v)}															

Notes: ^{a)} theoretical [39], FS-RCCSD; ^{b)} experimental [16]; ^{c)} theoretical [27], FS-RCCSD; ^{d)} theoretical [28], FS-RCCSD/Dyall basis set; ^{e)} theoretical [28], FS-RCCSD/RCC-ANO basis set; ^{f)} theoretical [25], FS-RCCSD; ^{g)} theoretical [26], CCSD(T); ^{h)} theoretical [30], FS-RCC; ⁱ⁾ theoretical [2], CCSD; ^{j)} this study, FS-RCCSD; ^{k)} experimental [15]; ^{l)} theoretical [35], CASSCF/XMCQDPT2+SOC; ^{m)} theoretical [33], FS-RCCSD; ⁿ⁾ theoretical [40], FS-RCCSD; ^{o)} theoretical [41], FS-RCCSD; **bold** – our calculations at the FS-RCCSD (terms) or MRCI (PDMs) levels of theory; underlined – experimental.

FIG. 2. (Color online) The dependencies of calculated SOC splitting ΔE_{SOC} upon internuclear distances for the $A^2\Pi$ and $B^2\Delta$ states of the RaF [39] (a), RaCl (b), RaBr [40] (c), RaI [41] (d), and RaAt (e) molecules. ΔE_{SOC} represents the difference between upper and lower components of the corresponding state.

These dependencies are typical for all considered radium monohalides. All of them demonstrate similar behavior due to similarity of the PECs near their minima. These dependencies are almost linear due to small values of the anharmonicity constants.

The calculated harmonic frequencies of the RaF and RaCl radicals are in good agreement with the experimental [15, 16] data: the errors are about 1 % or less for the RaF and 1–3 % for the RaCl. So, we believe that calculated harmonic frequencies and other spectroscopic molecular parameters for other radium monohalides are also close enough to the realistic values.

It is assumed that the high accuracy of

the reproduction of spectroscopic parameters, in its turn, ensures the correctness of radiative properties.

3.2. Franck–Condon factors and radiative properties

Based on the calculated PECs and vibrational energies, we predicted the Franck–Condon factors and vibrational branching ratios (VBRs), which, in contrast to FCFs, can be directly measured in a spectroscopic experiment. The VBRs were evaluated by the following equation:

Table 2: Molecular spectroscopic parameters (in cm^{-1}) of the lowest states of the radium monohalides molecules.

State	$^{226}\text{Ra}^{19}\text{F}$			$^{226}\text{Ra}^{35}\text{Cl}$			$^{226}\text{Ra}^{79}\text{Br}$			$^{226}\text{Ra}^{127}\text{I}$			$^{226}\text{Ra}^{210}\text{At}$		
	ω_e	$\omega_e\chi_e$	B_e	ω_e	$\omega_e\chi_e$	B_e	ω_e	$\omega_e\chi_e$	B_e	ω_e	$\omega_e\chi_e$	B_e	ω_e	$\omega_e\chi_e$	B_e
$X^2\Sigma^+$	438.4 ^{a)}														
	<u>441.8</u> ^{b)}														
	428.0 ^{c)}	1.62 ^{a)}	0.1858 ^{a)}	249.2 ^{j)}	0.631 ^{j)}	0.0700 ^{j)}	165.5 ⁿ⁾	0.382 ⁿ⁾	0.0321 ⁿ⁾	127.1 ^{o)}	0.185 ^{o)}	0.0198 ^{o)}	104.0 ^{j)}	0.124 ^{j)}	0.014 ^{j)}
	428.0 ^{d)}	<u>1.67</u> ^{b)}	0.1898 ^{d)}	<u>256.4</u> ^{k)}		0.0700 ⁱ⁾			0.033 ⁱ⁾			0.0200 ⁱ⁾			0.0140 ⁱ⁾
	431.0 ^{e)}	1.53 ^{f)}	0.1800 ⁱ⁾	254.5 ^{g)}											
	435.0 ^{f)}	1.65 ^{g)}		266.4 ^{l)}											
432.8 ^{g)}			258.5 ^{m)}												
440.6 ^{h)}															
$A^2\Pi_{1/2}$	437.2 ^{a)}														
	<u>435.5</u> ^{b)}														
	432.0 ^{c)}	1.62 ^{a)}	0.1857 ^{a)}	252.2 ^{j)}	0.734 ^{j)}	0.0702 ^{j)}	168.4 ⁿ⁾	0.338 ⁿ⁾	0.0323 ⁿ⁾	130.4 ^{o)}	0.182 ^{o)}	0.0200 ^{o)}	107.1 ^{j)}	0.149 ^{j)}	0.0141 ^{j)}
	432.0 ^{d)}	<u>1.64</u> ^{b)}		<u>255.0</u> ^{l)}											
	428.0 ^{e)}			259.0 ^{m)}											
	436.9 ^{h)}														
$B^2\Delta_{3/2}$	429.9 ^{a)}														
	<u>431.9</u> ^{b)}														
	432.0 ^{d)}	1.63 ^{a)}	0.1845 ^{a)}	244.3 ^{j)}	0.703 ^{j)}	0.0694 ^{j)}	163.1 ⁿ⁾	0.368 ⁿ⁾	0.0319 ⁿ⁾	126.4 ^{o)}	0.198 ^{o)}	0.0199 ^{o)}	103.6 ^{j)}	0.123 ^{j)}	0.0140 ^{j)}
	431.0 ^{e)}	<u>1.65</u> ^{b)}		<u>251.5</u> ^{l)}											
	430.8 ^{h)}			253.9 ^{m)}											
	441.0 ^{a)}			247.1 ^{j)}											
$B^2\Delta_{5/2}$	419.0 ^{d)}	1.52 ^{a)}	0.1863 ^{a)}	239.6 ^{l)}	0.720 ^{j)}	0.0698 ^{j)}	164.9 ⁿ⁾	0.353 ⁿ⁾	0.0321 ⁿ⁾	127.8 ^{o)}	0.189 ^{o)}	0.0200 ^{o)}	105.0 ^{j)}	0.139 ^{j)}	0.0141 ^{j)}
	423.0 ^{e)}			256.3 ^{m)}											
	433.9 ^{h)}														
	424.5 ^{a)}			251.0 ^{j)}											
	<u>419.1</u> ^{b)}			<u>254.0</u> ^{k)}											
	410.0 ^{d)}	1.75 ^{a)}	0.1838 ^{a)}	245.3 ^{l)}	0.744 ^{j)}	0.0702 ^{j)}	167.1 ⁿ⁾	0.342 ⁿ⁾	0.0322 ⁿ⁾	129.3 ^{o)}	0.187 ^{o)}	0.0200 ^{o)}	105.9 ^{j)}	0.145 ^{j)}	0.0141 ^{j)}
$A^2\Pi_{3/2}$	415.0 ^{e)}			257.2 ^{m)}											
	436.4 ^{h)}														
	430.6 ^{a)}			249.0 ^{j)}											
	<u>430.9</u> ^{b)}			<u>253.2</u> ^{k)}											
	416.0 ^{d)}	1.63 ^{a)}	0.1834 ^{a)}	262.8 ^{l)}	0.729 ^{j)}	0.0698 ^{j)}	166.9 ⁿ⁾	0.358 ⁿ⁾	0.0322 ⁿ⁾	129.9 ^{o)}	0.190 ^{o)}	0.0200 ^{o)}	106.8 ^{j)}	0.154 ^{j)}	0.0141 ^{j)}
	419.0 ^{e)}	<u>1.67</u> ^{b)}		256.6 ^{m)}											
432.1 ^{h)}															

Notes: ^{a)} theoretical [39], FS-RCCSD; ^{b)} experimental [16]; ^{c)} theoretical [16]; ^{d)} theoretical [27], FS-RCCSD; ^{e)} theoretical [28], FS-RCCSD/Dyall basis set; ^{f)} theoretical [28], FS-RCCSD/RCC-ANO basis set; ^{g)} theoretical [25], FS-RCCSD; ^{h)} theoretical [26], CCSD(T); ⁱ⁾ theoretical [30], FS-RCC; ^{j)} theoretical [2], CCSD; ^{k)} experimental [15]; ^{l)} theoretical [35], CASSCF/XMCQDPT2+SOC; ^{m)} theoretical [33], FS-RCCSD; ⁿ⁾ theoretical [40], FS-RCCSD; ^{o)} theoretical [41], FS-RCCSD; **bold** – our calculations at the FS-RCCSD (terms) or MRCI (PDMs) levels of theory; underlined – experimental.

FIG. 3. (Color online) The dependencies of calculated permanent dipole moments upon internuclear distances of the RaF [39] (a), RaCl (b), RaBr [40] (c), RaI [41] (d), and RaAt (e) molecules.

$$b_{v'v''} = \frac{A_{v'v''}}{\sum_k A_{v'k}} = \frac{f_{v'v''}(\Delta E_{v'v''})^3}{\sum_k f_{v'k}(\Delta E_{v'k})^3}, \quad (3.1)$$

where v' and v'' are numbers of upper and lower vibrational levels; $A_{v'v''}$, $f_{v'v''}$, and $\Delta E_{v'v''}$ are the Einstein coefficient for spontaneous emission, the FCF, and the energy difference between v' and v'' states, respectively.

The FCFs and VBRs were calculated for the $A^2\Pi_{1/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$, $A^2\Pi_{3/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$, and $C^2\Sigma^+ \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$ allowed vibronic transitions. Since the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}$ state is a lower excited one, the $A^2\Pi_{1/2} \leftrightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$ channel satisfies at least two Di Rosa's criteria [3] and is considered as the

most advantageous for direct laser cooling. The FCFs distributions for the transitions between the lowest vibrational states of the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}$ and $X^2\Sigma^+$ terms are shown in Fig. 5. The calculated FCFs and VBRs for the $A^2\Pi_{1/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$ band system are listed in Table 3.

Fig. 5 demonstrates the differences between diagonal and off-diagonal FCFs and underlines their more or less diagonal distributions. The closer the values are to unity, the more concentrated their distribution along the diagonal. This is distinctly visible for RaF and RaCl and less so for RaI, while for RaBr and RaAt the distribution exhibits more of a diffuse character. In other words, it shows the fulfilment

FIG. 4. (Color online) The dependencies of vibrational energies E_v upon vibrational number v for the low-lying states of the $^{226}\text{Ra}^{19}\text{F}$ [39] (a), $^{226}\text{Ra}^{35}\text{Cl}$ (b), $^{226}\text{Ra}^{79}\text{Br}$ [40] (c), $^{226}\text{Ra}^{127}\text{I}$ [41] (d), and $^{226}\text{Ra}^{210}\text{At}$ (e) molecules.

of the second Di Rosa's condition [3] for all the radicals under consideration and especially for RaF and RaCl, and proves they are suitable candidates for direct laser cooling.

The radiative decays in diagonal channels ($v' = v''$) are slightly enhanced when the energy difference is taken into account (VBRs for these transitions are slightly larger than FCF).

Diagonal FCFs for the $A^2\Pi_{1/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$ transitions demonstrate the trend to decreasing in a series of the RaF, RaCl, RaBr, RaI, and RaAt molecules. E. g., the $0' \rightarrow 0''$ FCF is equal to 0.999998 (RaF, [39]), 0.998330 (RaCl), 0.990752 (RaBr [40]), 0.954439 (RaI [41]), and 0.949196 (RaAt). Our calculated value for the $0' \rightarrow 0''$ FCF for the radium monochloride (0.998330) is slightly less than Isaev *et al.* [33] one (0.998516).

The $0' \rightarrow 0''$ FCF for the radium monofluoride is the largest among all monofluorides of alkaline earth metals: 0.897 (BeF [51]), 0.917 (MgF [52]), 0.98 (CaF [53]), 0.98 (SrF [6, 7]), 0.980 (BaF [54]), and 0.999998 (RaF, [39]).

This emphasizes the assumption that the RaF radical is one of the most promising diatomics for direct laser cooling. Relatively small values of the $0' \rightarrow 0''$ FCF of the BeF and MgF radicals can be explained in the framework of difference between two types of chemical bonding. In the beryllium and magnesium monohalides the chemical bond has a partial covalent character, in contrast to other monohalides of alkaline earth metals, which are almost pure ionic compounds.

FIG. 5. (Color online) The distributions of calculated FCFs for the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v') \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+(v'')$, $v', v'' = 0, \dots, 9$ vibronic transitions of the RaF [39] (a), RaCl (b), RaBr [40] (c), RaI [41] (d), and RaAt (e) molecules.

The contribution of the ionic bonding is enhanced when the atomic number of the alkaline earth metal increases. This is reflected in the increasing similarity of the PEC of excited states to the PEC of the ground state and, as a result, in the increasing of the diagonal FCFs. The electronic transition moments in the Franck–Condon region demonstrate a linear or quasi-linear behavior (see Fig. 6. In this case, the dependence of TDMs on the internuclear distance can be neglected, and TDMs for the minima of PECs were used for the evaluation of the radiative properties.

Based on the calculated TDMs, FCFs, and vibrational levels, the lifetimes $\tau_{v'}$ (in seconds) of vibrational levels v' were estimated according to

the following equation:

$$\tau_{v'} = \frac{1}{A_{v'}} = \frac{k}{|TDM|^2 \sum_{v''} f_{v'v''} (\Delta E_{v'v''})^3}, \quad (3.2)$$

where $A_{v'}$ is the Einstein coefficient for spontaneous emission, $k = 4.936 \times 10^5$, $|TDM|^2$ is the sum of the squares of absolute values of components of electronic transition dipole moment (in a.u.), $\Delta E_{v'v''}$ are in cm^{-1} .

The Einstein coefficients $A_{v'v''}$ and radiative lifetimes $\tau_{v'}$ of the lowest vibrational level $v' = 0$ for the $A^2\Pi_{1/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$, $A^2\Pi_{3/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$, and $C^2\Sigma^+ \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$ vibronic transitions are summarized in Table 4. All calculated lifetimes are tens of nanoseconds, which provides high

FIG. 6. (Color online) The dependencies of calculated transition dipole moments upon internuclear distances for the $A^2\Pi_{1/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$, $B^2\Delta_{3/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$, $B^2\Delta_{3/2} \rightarrow A^2\Pi_{1/2}$, $A^2\Pi_{3/2} \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$, $C^2\Sigma^+ \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+$, and $C^2\Sigma^+ \rightarrow A^2\Pi_{1/2}$ transitions of the RaF [39] (a), RaCl (b), RaBr [40] (c), RaI [41] (d), and RaAt (e) molecules.

values of the Einstein coefficients for spontaneous emission and satisfies the first Di Rosa's criterion [3]. The calculated lifetime of the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0)$ state for the radium monofluoride (42.8 ns) agrees with the upper experimental limit for this state (≤ 50 ns) [16]. Our calculated lifetime of the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0)$ state for the radium monochloride (31.9 ns) is less than the value estimated by the data of Isaev et al [33] (50.6 ns) due to the differences in TDM values.

3.3. Cooling parameters

The change in velocity of a molecule upon each scattering act, or recoil velocity, is $v_r = h/(M\lambda)$ [55], where h is the Planck's constant; M is the mass of a molecule; λ is the laser wavelength. Due to the large mass of the molecules under consideration, this quantity varies from 0.22 to 0.11 cm/s (for details see Table 5).

A typical speed of the molecules in a room temperature v_{room} lies in the range from 173 to 130 m/s, therefore it is necessary to provide from 80000 to 115000 absorption/emission cycles (N_{room}) to decrease this speed close to zero.

Table 3. The calculated FCFs and VBRs for the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v') \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+(v'')$, $v', v'' = 0, \dots, 3$ vibronic transitions of the radium monohalides.

$v' \rightarrow v''$	$^{226}\text{Ra}^{19}\text{F}$		$^{226}\text{Ra}^{35}\text{Cl}$		$^{226}\text{Ra}^{79}\text{Br}$		$^{226}\text{Ra}^{127}\text{I}$		$^{226}\text{Ra}^{210}\text{At}$	
	$f_{v'v''}$	$b_{v'v''}$	$f_{v'v''}$	$b_{v'v''}$	$f_{v'v''}$	$b_{v'v''}$	$f_{v'v''}$	$b_{v'v''}$	$f_{v'v''}$	$b_{v'v''}$
0→0	0.999998	0.999999	0.998330	0.998425	0.990752	0.991108	0.954439	0.955799	0.949196	0.950442
0→1	1.0×10^{-6}	0	0.001667	0.001575	0.009200	0.008848	0.044265	0.042982	0.049298	0.048126
0→2	0	0	0	0	0.000046	0.000044	0.001266	0.001192	0.001473	0.001401
0→3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.000028	0.000026	0.000032	0.000030
1→0	0	1.0×10^{-6}	0.001667	0.001765	0.009209	0.009577	0.044720	0.046170	0.049661	0.050992
1→1	0.999995	0.999996	0.994957	0.995049	0.972319	0.972660	0.867398	0.868604	0.852478	0.85358
1→2	1.8×10^{-6}	1.6×10^{-6}	0.003375	0.003184	0.018327	0.017628	0.084090	0.081659	0.093458	0.091241
1→3	0	0	1.5×10^{-6}	1.3×10^{-6}	0.000145	0.000134	0.003679	0.003463	0.004273	0.004066
2→0	0	0	3.6×10^{-6}	4.0×10^{-6}	0.000039	0.000042	0.000833	0.000886	0.001128	0.001188
2→1	1.8×10^{-6}	2.0×10^{-6}	0.003364	0.003562	0.018363	0.019094	0.085863	0.088634	0.094850	0.097384
2→2	0.999991	0.999992	0.991487	0.991578	0.953937	0.954264	0.786019	0.787090	0.762571	0.763544
2→3	2.3×10^{-6}	2.5×10^{-6}	0.005141	0.004853	0.027366	0.026327	0.119886	0.116429	0.132866	0.129721
3→0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.000007	0.000008	0.000014	0.000015
3→1	2.0×10^{-6}	2.4×10^{-6}	9.0×10^{-6}	0.000010	0.000117	0.000127	0.002445	0.002601	0.003317	0.003492
3→2	2.4×10^{-6}	2.6×10^{-6}	0.005119	0.005418	0.027453	0.028541	0.123752	0.127729	0.135869	0.139485
3→3	0.999986	0.999987	0.987955	0.988041	0.935612	0.935925	0.709968	0.710914	0.679320	0.680171

However, the preliminary buffer gas cooling can reduce the temperature up to 3 K, which corresponds to a typical speed of the molecules v_{3K} from 17 to 13 m/s. Hence, the number of required scattering acts (N_{3K}) is reduced to about 10000, which should be considered a lower goal limit for realizing the effective direct cooling scheme.

The number of scattered photons when using only one channel $0' - 0''$ is defined as:

$$N_{ph} = \frac{1}{1 - f_{00}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where f_{00} is a FCF for the $0' - 0''$ transition [55].

According to our calculations, the FCF for the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0) \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+(v'' = 0)$ provides the required number of scattered photons (500

000) only for the RaF molecule. For the other radium monohalides this quantity varies from 600 to 20, which is not enough for the realization of the closed optical scheme of direct laser cooling. Nevertheless, in concordance with Di Rosa's [3] suggestion, the inclusion in the cooling cycle of not only the ground vibrational level $v'' = 0$ but also some number of excited vibrational levels ($v'' = 1, 2, \dots$) could provide the complete probability for the molecule being cooled to remain in the cooling loop close to unity and realize a quasi-closed optical scheme.

In this case, the last equation is transformed into

$$N_{ph} = \frac{1}{1 - \sum_{v''} f_{0v''}}. \quad (3.4)$$

As a result, the required number of scattered photons for the RaCl molecule is achieved using two channels ($v'' = 0, 1$), and for other radium monohalides, through three channels ($v'' = 0, 1, 2$). Adding one more transition ($v'' = 3$) for the RaI and RaAt radicals increases N_{ph} up to 500000.

The Doppler temperature T_D , or the minimum temperature, which can be achieved by the Doppler cooling, can be calculated using the following equation:

$$T_D = -\frac{h\Gamma^2}{16\pi k_B \Delta} \left(1 + \frac{I}{I_s} + \frac{4\Delta^2}{\Gamma^2}\right), \quad (3.5)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann's constant; Γ is a natural linewidth, which is related to a radiative lifetime ($\Gamma = 1/\tau$); Δ is a detuning parameter; I is an intensity of laser beam; I_s is the saturation intensity, which is defined as $I_s = \pi h c \Gamma / (3\lambda^3)$, where c is the speed of light. If $\Delta = -\Gamma/2$ and $I \ll I_s$, the minimal Doppler temperature T_D^{min} , or the Doppler limit, is

$$T_D^{min} = \frac{h\Gamma}{4\pi k_B}. \quad (3.6)$$

Using the lifetime values calculated earlier, the minimal Doppler temperature for the radium monohalides is about 100 μ K. However, if one takes into account the typical experimental conditions, it is possible to evaluate a more realistic Doppler temperature T_D . If the detuning parameter $\Delta = -\Gamma/2$ and typical intensity of a laser beam $I = 100$ mW/cm² (see, for example, experiment on CaF laser cooling [56]), the Doppler temperature T_D is evaluated to about 5 mK. This temperature strongly depends on the detuning parameter Δ . In all cases, the Doppler temperature has reached a minimum at $\Delta \approx -2\Gamma$, and the optimal choice of the detuning parameter reduces the T_D^{opt} temperature by about two times (see Table 5).

Finally, the recoil temperature T_r , or sub-Doppler cooling temperature, which can be reached by using, for example, the Sisyphus method, is calculated by the equation:

$$T_r = \frac{h^2}{Mk_B\lambda^2}. \quad (3.7)$$

From an efficiency perspective of the direct laser cooling scheme, among all radium monohalides the radium monofluoride molecule looks the most promising due to the highest values of diagonal FCFs, which provides the least number of required lasers to realize the cooling scheme. Nevertheless, the heavier diatomics also have some advantages. The increase of mass of a molecule and excitation wavelength in the series RaF \rightarrow RaCl \rightarrow RaBr \rightarrow RaI \rightarrow RaAt reduces recoil T_r temperature. This quantity varies from 138 nK (RaF) to 66 nK (RaAt), and for the RaAt medium, it seems possible to achieve a recoil temperature two times lower than for the RaF one.

3.4. Cooling schemes

The generalized vibrational cooling scheme, including one pump and one (RaCl) or two (RaBr, RaI, and RaAt) repump lasers [7] is shown in Fig. 7. The main laser with the wavelength $\lambda_{00} = 752.7$ (RaF), 780.4 (RaCl), 791.4 (RaBr), 806.9 (RaI), or 811.9 nm (RaAt) drives the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0) \rightarrow X^2\Sigma^+(v'' = 0)$ transition.

For the RaF molecule almost all decays ($f_{00} = 0.999998$, $b_{00} = 0.999999$) from the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0)$ state return molecules to the $X^2\Sigma^+(v'' = 0)$ state and there is a vanishingly small ($f_{01} = 0.000001$, $f_{02+} = 0.000001$) probability of decay from the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0)$ state to the $X^2\Sigma^+(v'' = 1, 2, \dots)$ states. Thus, it is assumed that the cooling scheme for the RaF molecule can be realized using only one pump laser.

For the RaCl molecule, main cooling channel ($f_{00} = 0.998330$) provides about 600 photon absorption/emission cycles, and additional repump laser with the wavelength $\lambda_{10} = 795.8$ nm returns the population from the $X^2\Sigma^+(v'' = 1)$ state to the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0)$ state ($f_{01} = 0.001667$). In this case, the number of scattered photons per molecule increases up to

Table 4. The Einstein coefficients A_0 (in 1/s) and radiative lifetimes τ_0 (in ns) for the allowed vibronic transition to the ground $X^2\Sigma^+$ state of the radium monohalides.

Transition	$^{226}\text{Ra}^{19}\text{F}$		$^{226}\text{Ra}^{35}\text{Cl}$		$^{226}\text{Ra}^{79}\text{Br}$		$^{226}\text{Ra}^{127}\text{I}$		$^{226}\text{Ra}^{210}\text{At}$	
	$A_0 \Gamma - 10^{-7}$	τ_0	$A_0 \Gamma - 10^{-7}$	τ_0	$A_0 \Gamma - 10^{-7}$	τ_0	$A_0 \Gamma - 10^{-7}$	τ_0	$A_0 \Gamma - 10^{-7}$	τ_0
$A^2\Pi_{1/2} \text{ B}\dagger' \ X^2\Sigma^+$	2.334	42.8	3.130	31.9	1.577	63.4	2.747	36.4	2.703	37.0
$A^2\Pi_{3/2} \text{ B}\dagger' \ X^2\Sigma^+$	3.367	29.7	4.577	21.8	2.175	46.0	4.080	24.5	4.012	24.9
$C^2\Sigma^+ \text{ B}\dagger' \ X^2\Sigma^+$	5.263	19.0	3.419	29.2	3.019	33.1	2.888	34.6	2.812	35.6

Table 5: Some cooling parameters for the radium monohalides.

	v_r , cm/s	v_{room} , m/s	v_{3K} , m/s	N_{room}	N_{3K}	N_{ph}			T_D , mK	T_D^{min} , μK	T_D^{opt} , mK	T_r , nK
						00	00+01	00+01+02				
$^{226}\text{Ra}^{19}\text{F}$	0.22	173	17	80 000	8100	500 000	–	–	4.50	90	2.2	138
$^{226}\text{Ra}^{35}\text{Cl}$	0.20	167	17	85 000	8800	600	330 000	–	5.1	120	2.7	120
$^{226}\text{Ra}^{79}\text{Br}$	0.17	155	16	94 000	9500	100	20 000	500 000	4.9	60	1.9	100
$^{226}\text{Ra}^{127}\text{I}$	0.14	144	15	103 000	10 500	22	770	33 000	5.5	105	2.6	83
$^{226}\text{Ra}^{210}\text{At}$	0.11	130	13	115 000	11 600	20	660	30 000	5.6	103	2.6	66

 FIG. 7. Vibrational laser cooling scheme for the radium monohalides molecules using the $A^2\Pi_{1/2} (v') \leftarrow X^2\Sigma^+ (v'')$ pump transitions (solid lines) and spontaneous decay (dashed lines).

330 000. So, the cooling scheme for the RaCl molecule is assumed to use one pump and one

repump laser.

For the other radium monohalides molecules, the main pumping channel can provide only 100 (RaBr) or 20 (RaI and RaAt) scatterings. Therefore, the first additional repump laser with the wavelength $\lambda_{10} = 801.8$ (RaBr), 815.3 (RaI), or 818.8 nm (RaAt) returns the population directly from the $X^2\Sigma^+(v'' = 1)$ state to the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0)$ state. The second additional repump laser with the wavelength $\lambda_{21} = 801.6$ (RaBr), 815.0 (RaI), or 818.6 nm (RaAt) returns the population indirectly to the main cycle by driving the $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 1) \leftarrow X^2\Sigma^+(v'' = 2)$ transition. Alternative second repump channel may include direct $A^2\Pi_{1/2}(v' = 0) \leftarrow X^2\Sigma^+(v'' = 2)$ transition with the wavelength $\lambda_{20} = 812.5$ (RaBr), 823.7 (RaI), or 825.8 nm (RaAt). In the case of the RaBr molecule the number of scattered photons per molecule increases up to 500 000, for the RaI and RaAt radicals this number is about 30 000, which is three times more than the mentioned earlier lower limit. So, the cooling scheme for the RaBr, RaI, and RaAt molecules is assumed to use

one pump and two repump lasers.

Elimination of the rotational branching is provided by the $J' = 0 \leftarrow J'' = 1$ type transition (where J is rotational angular momentum quantum number). This leads to the optical pumping into the dark Zeeman sublevels, which can be avoided by their remixing [1, 55].

The wavelengths of all transitions under consideration fall into the peak power output (750-850 nm) of the tunable Ti:sapphire laser [57], which makes it potentially the most suitable source for practical realization of the cooling scheme.

4. Conclusions

Based on the state-of-the-art quantum chemical calculations at the high level of theory (FS-RCCSD), the molecular spectroscopic parameters of the lowest terms, as well as radiative properties of the vibronic states of the radium monochloride RaCl and radium monoastatide RaAt radicals are predicted. In combination with previous studies of the RaF, RaBr, and RaI diatomic molecules, now it is possible to obtain a comparative characteristic of spectroscopic properties of all radium monohalides. Calculated results correspond to the trend of other studied analogues and can be used for further spectroscopic experiments with the radium monohalides.

The possibilities for the realization of closed

or quasi-closed schemes for the direct laser cooling involving ground $X^2\Sigma^+$ and first excited $A^2\Pi_{1/2}$ states are also considered. The preliminary buffer gas cooling and the use of one-color (RaF), two-color (RaCl), or three-color (RaBr, RaI, and RaAt) laser schemes allow to ensure the fulfillment of the conditions for direct laser cooling and to realize a close (RaF) or a quasi-closed (other radium monohalides) optical cycle for effective cooling of the dilute radium monohalides gas media.

The obtained results in this study are in good agreement with previous theoretical and experimental research on the subject. It is shown that spectroscopic parameters of radium monohalides are fitting for the successful realization of direct laser cooling. While RaF is proven to be the most promising candidate among the studied molecules, all five diatomics are of interest for laser cooling and its possible applications, due to their unique molecular spectroscopic properties.

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